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Cloud-Based Databases: Security and Privacy Challenges

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Abstract

In the current technological landscape, sophistication has become a hallmark, epitomized by the advent of Cloud Computing. This innovation extends to Cloud databases, which represent a significant application of Cloud Computing, offering scalable and efficient data management solutions. However, the shift towards cloud-based environments introduces risks regarding privacy and security. Despite advancements in cloud technologies, this paper reveals persistent vulnerabilities, including data breaches and external attacks, underscoring the challenges in safeguarding cloud databases. Cloud service providers are equipped with robust technologies designed to enhance data privacy and security. To mitigate these risks, a comprehensive approach encompassing encryption techniques, stringent access control measures, and independent third-party audits is essential. These strategies are integral to reinforcing the security framework, ensuring that data privacy and security are upheld within cloud service platforms. By leveraging the capabilities of cloud service providers and adopting these procedural technologies, stakeholders can achieve a secure cloud computing environment, thereby fostering trust and reliability in cloud database systems.

Introduction

The advancement of human processes has been propelled by technology over the years. People are useful in living their lives and performing their occupations because of technological advancements. The existence of cloud computing is one example of the current wave of technical developments. RAJ, M. n.d. states that cloud computing offers on-demand computational and storage resources. Since data is hosted in the cloud, users of cloud computing can save and retrieve data remotely. There are several benefits to cloud computing. In the first place, cloud computing is quick and very adaptable, making access simple when required. By sharing resources and utilising virtualization, cloud computing can also lower costs. A cloud database is one of the services offered by cloud computing. The cloud is used to create and access cloud databases. Because this study on cloud computing security and privacy has been found so frequently, it offers current research on cloud databases. It is acknowledged that the development of cloud computing represents a major technological achievement. Through the effective distribution of computer resources and services via the internet, cloud computing enables users to access and control data and applications from a remote location.

One crucial consideration when utilising a cloud-based database is data protection and privacy. Security and privacy of data are two important considerations that need to be made. Rodriguez et al. (2013) state that while cloud computing has been a useful technology, we cannot be certain that our privacy and data security are adequately secured. Numerous factors, including a lack of control over data, concerns with data transactions, problems with ethics and trust, and external threats, might impact data privacy and security. This study examines how secure and private cloud databases may be, as well as how to keep them that way.

Cloud database services are currently offered by numerous platforms, including Oracle, Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services, and many more; nonetheless, these three are the most popular among users. Alone, Amazon Web Services boasts almost a million active users. Because AWS offers so many services, including AWS Lambda, Amazon DynamoDB, Amazon RedShift, and others, a lot of people opt for AWS. According to Azure Directory data from 2022 and 2023, Microsoft Azure boasts a user base of over 722 million. Azure Data Explorer, Microsoft Azure SQL Database, and many other services are provided by Microsoft Azure itself. Regarding Oracle, it processes at least 33 billion transactions every day and has over 70 million users now. The purpose of this research paper is to offer insights into answering the research question by presenting a literature review of security and privacy challenges in cloud-based databases. The first section provides an overview of the study's background and significance, highlighting the main driving forces for the investigation. A comprehensive analysis of the current literature review is provided in Section 2. In Section 3, the approach used to address the goals of the research is discussed. In Section 4, the research question is addressed. The main conclusions drawn from the study are finally summarized in the concluding section.

Literature Review

Cloud computing has become a fundamental aspect of modern technology due to its effectiveness and unparalleled flexibility, which significantly contributes to its widespread adoption. This innovative computing paradigm offers extensive scalability and on-demand resources, enabling users to access computing services over the internet without the need for extensive physical infrastructure. Such flexibility not only enhances operational efficiency but also facilitates remote work and global collaboration, as highlighted by Win & Thaw (n.d.).

A wide range of service providers, each providing distinctive platforms and services catered to different corporate needs, enrich the cloud computing ecosystem. Industry titans like Microsoft Azure, Oracle, and Amazon Web Services (AWS) are leading the way. These providers deliver a comprehensive range of services, from infrastructure as a service (IaaS) and platform as a service (PaaS) to software as a service (SaaS), catering to the intricate requirements of modern businesses and developers. The diversity and quality of services available make cloud computing an indispensable tool for companies aiming to stay competitive in the digital age, driving innovation and enabling seamless collaboration across the globe.

1. Software as a Service (SaaS)

In the SaaS model, cloud service providers offer software that can be managed and used. By using SaaS, cloud users do not need to make any upfront investment, and costs are usually low since only one application exists. This SaaS model offers scalability from customer to provider for higher efficiencies. To use this SaaS model, users do not need in-depth infrastructure knowledge, Win & Thaw, (n.d). SaaS can be said to be the best choice for many business

companies because using SaaS makes it possible to accelerate business development with the latest technology available

Fig. 1 Benefits of SaaS

2. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) stands as a pivotal component of cloud computing, providing essential resources such as storage, computing power, and networking capabilities, all accessible remotely. This model allows for the dynamic provisioning of virtualized computing infrastructure over the internet, enabling businesses to configure and manage cloud servers according to specific requirements. By adopting IaaS, organizations can eliminate the need for costly physical hardware, opting instead for a flexible, cost-effective solution that aligns with their operational demands.

The versatility of IaaS is particularly beneficial for companies seeking to store vast amounts of data without the burden of managing physical servers. It offers a scalable framework, allowing

businesses to adjust their resource utilization based on fluctuating processing and storage needs. This adaptability ensures that companies can efficiently handle peak loads and scale down during quieter periods, optimizing cost and performance. IaaS providers facilitate access to a broad spectrum of resources, including advanced computing power, expansive network capabilities, and substantial storage solutions. This access empowers users to deploy a wide range of applications and services, from simple website hosting to complex data analytics operations. The model's pay-as-you-go pricing structure further enhances its appeal, providing businesses with the flexibility to invest in additional resources only as needed.

As noted by Akhtar et al. (2021), the convenience and scalability offered by IaaS make it an indispensable tool for modern businesses. It supports rapid deployment and agile management of digital infrastructure, enabling organizations to remain competitive in a fast-paced digital landscape. By leveraging IaaS, companies can focus on innovation and growth, leaving the complexities of infrastructure management to specialized providers. This strategic approach to IT infrastructure is reshaping how businesses operate, driving efficiency, and fostering technological advancement across industries.

Fig. 2 IaaS Benefits

3. Product as a Service (PaaS)

PaaS provides development environments and the software layer as a service. Unlike SaaS, PaaS allows customers to build their own apps, but those apps continue to use the provider's infrastructure. Tabrizchi and Rafsanjani, Kuchaki (2020). It is possible to say that users are free to create their own apps. While the user has control over the apps within the environment, the operating system is beyond their control. The most common use case for PaaS is in application development. Users don't have to spend money to get the developer tools they need to construct and manage apps thanks to PaaS. Among the various uses for cloud computing are:

1. One example of a service that uses cloud-based data storage is smart health. Chenthara & associates, 2019.
2. Database that is cloud-based.
3. A traffic management system called VANET transmits safety messages between cars in an effort to protect human life while driving and to make travellers more comfortable..
4. CoT (Cloud of Things) combines modern cloud technology and IoT.
5. Hadoop is useful for handling big data where Hadoop works in the cloud.

A cloud environment presents several privacy and security-related challenges and barriers. In 2019, Chakrabarti et al. A state of security is one that is free from danger and disruption, according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI). Another way to define security would be as a concealed or protected state. One way to think of privacy is as freedom and solitude. Users of cloud computing, particularly cloud databases, want their data to be safe against harm and unintentional access, as well as private. Users most definitely don't want their info to get lost or

spread. The things that require consideration include security and privacy, according to Sun (2019). Security and privacy concerns must be resolved right away by creating effective defense and security measures. Enhancing cloud security and defense can be done in a variety of ways. It's difficult to apply every strategy. The system's overall robustness and performance are decreased when more security mechanisms are added. Cloud databases, for instance, need to be economical, easy to maintain, and responsive. Losing control over data and being entirely dependent on cloud computing companies are the two key issues with security and privacy. Cloud privacy is an issue because cloud computing allows for remote data storage and dynamic service sharing. Because of this, managing personal data and maintaining control over it presents a difficulty for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) that use cloud services. Additionally, privacy concerns need complete security and responsible use of consumer personal information. Wang, 2022. Errors in the configuration of the web server typically led to vulnerabilities. Transparency from users and data confidentiality are essential in cloud computing. The migration of generic internal software code to public clouds, security standardization initiatives, quick user provisioning in the cloud, privacy protection strategies, better cloud providers' compliance with regulations and disclosure standards, and software-tested infrastructure and configurations are also less crucial. To improve cloud database security, a number of technologies can be applied, such as.

Fig. 3 PaaS Benefits

1. Blockchain technology, renowned for its revolutionary approach to secure and immutable record-keeping, primarily focuses on transactions of relatively small data sizes. At its core, blockchain leverages advanced encryption and cryptography to safeguard data, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of transactions recorded on its distributed ledger. This encryption not only secures the data but also offers users a degree of flexibility in terms of the sequence and variety of their transactions, enhancing user experience without compromising security.

However, despite its strengths, blockchain technology faces challenges related to the performance of cryptographic operations. The encryption technologies employed by blockchain systems are crucial for maintaining security; yet, they also introduce computational overheads. These overheads can impact the speed and efficiency of

blockchain transactions, particularly when performing complex computations on encrypted data. Current cryptographic techniques, while effective in securing data, often require significant computational resources, leading to delays and inefficiencies in processing blockchain transactions. To address these challenges and enhance the performance of blockchain systems, there is a pressing need for the development of new cryptographic methods. Innovations in cryptography could potentially reduce the computational burden associated with encryption and decryption processes, thereby speeding up transaction processing times without sacrificing security. Such advancements would not only improve the overall efficiency of blockchain technology but also expand its applicability to a broader range of use cases that demand quick and secure transaction processing.

2. STRIDE analysis stands as a comprehensive framework in the term of computer security, designed to systematically identify and mitigate known threats within a system. This acronym encapsulates six core threat categories: Spoofing identity, Tampering with data, Repudiation threats, Information disclosure, Denial of service, and Elevation of privilege. By meticulously analyzing these aspects, STRIDE enables the development of robust security specifications aimed at safeguarding data privacy and integrity across digital platforms.

The application of STRIDE is particularly relevant in the context of cloud computing, where the security and privacy of cloud-based databases are of paramount concern. As businesses and individuals increasingly rely on cloud services for data storage and processing, the imperative to protect sensitive information from unauthorized access and

potential breaches has never been more critical. STRIDE's holistic approach to threat identification and mitigation plays a vital role in ensuring that cloud-based databases remain secure and resilient against a diverse range of cybersecurity threats.

Furthermore, the dynamic nature of cloud computing necessitates the continual evolution of security technologies. As Domingo-Ferrer (2019) highlights, users of cloud-based databases demand assurance that their data remains protected against infiltration and theft. In response, the field is witnessing the emergence of innovative security solutions designed to address the unique challenges of cloud computing. These advancements, coupled with established frameworks like STRIDE, contribute to a more secure digital environment where privacy and data security are maintained.

Given the ongoing advancements in cloud technology and the ever-expanding threat landscape, it is crucial for security frameworks and technologies to adapt and evolve. STRIDE, with its foundational principles, serves as a critical tool in this endeavor, guiding the development of effective security measures that can keep pace with the complexities of modern cloud-based systems.

Methodology

A. Search Keywords

The search query "Privacy and Security Challenges on Cloud Database" is used while conducting this research, along with the phrases "Privacy and Security Challenges" and "Cloud Database." Use digital libraries such as Google Scholar and Google to obtain relevant articles and images for your sources. Moreover, other relevant papers were discovered through the utilization of the aforementioned search terms and phrases.

Table 1. Literature Review Criteria

Inclusive Criteria	Exclusive Criteria
Studies that address cloud databases	The article was released in 2013
Studies that address cloud computing	Unidentified references in paper

B. Search Process

Using the previously indicated search term, Privacy and Security Challenges on Cloud Database, a Google Scholar and IEEE search was performed. The Google Scholar system uncovered earlier research articles and still deemed them relevant. Prior to writing this research paper, more than thirty other research papers and publications were examined.

C. Research Questions

1. In cloud databases, what privacy concerns might emerge?
2. What security challenges might cloud databases present?

3. How can cloud databases be protected against cyberattacks?
4. How can compromised databases be managed to restore the security of the data contained in the cloud database?

Result and Discussion

A. In cloud databases, what privacy concerns might emerge?

In a cloud database, problems will arise, one of which is a problem related to privacy. The following are privacy concerns in cloud databases.

- **Loss of Control Over data:** In cloud databases, users often face the dilemma of losing control over their data. Upon uploading data to the cloud, users might find themselves with limited access or diminished control, heightening concerns about data sovereignty. This apprehension is compounded by the reliance on uniform technical standards across the cloud, irrespective of the nature of the stored information. Such standardization can leave users feeling disconnected from their data, fostering worries about data security and privacy. Moreover, the increasing instances of service providers sharing user data with third parties have escalated these fears. This practice poses significant risks to user privacy, underscoring the critical need for stringent data protection measures and transparent policies to safeguard user interests in the cloud computing ecosystem.
- **Virtualization:** When talking about a cloud environment, it will be very closely related to virtualization. In virtualization, a new issue emerges, namely VM hopping, which is an attack that allows compromising VM projections and provides a separate way to access the hypervisor and other VMs.
- **Data manipulation:** Rogue cloud service providers will likely manipulate user data stored in the cloud. The manipulated data will be used to their advantage or may be shared. Therefore, before using cloud services, users must be selective. Do not let users use cloud

services that are considered cheap and provide many benefits but have not yet been tested for privacy.

B. What security challenges might cloud databases present?

Before we use a cloud database, of course, we also have to pay attention to important factors, including data security. The following are some security cases that may occur.

- **Hacking:** Hacking targets are usually sensitive data.
- Hacking that can happen is hacking the cloud security system or user accounts. This, of course, will be dangerous. Hackers who manage to enter have full authority to do anything to the account that will be misused.
- **Denial of Service (DoS):** DoS occurs when the system receives too much traffic. Most DoS attacks occur in large organizations like the banking sector and governments. When a DoS attack occurs, data will be lost. Recovering data will take time.
- **Spoofing attacks:** In a spoofing attack, malicious parties will try to impersonate other devices on the network or impersonate a user to carry out attacks, spread malware, and steal data.
- **Man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks:** MITM attacks are common attacks. This attack attackers can eavesdrop on communications between legitimate senders and legitimate recipients without their knowledge. In addition, this attack can also intercept sensitive data packets during data transmission, and the data will be replaced.

C. How can cloud databases be protected against cyberattacks?

Cloud database services is a broad and diverse field, with numerous providers offering their unique platforms, each equipped with specialized security measures to combat cyber threats. Leading the charge in this domain are giants such as Amazon Web Services, Microsoft's Azure, Oracle Databases, among others. These providers have set the benchmark for security within the cloud computing industry, developing proprietary technologies to ensure the safety and integrity of user data stored in their cloud environments.

Amazon AWS Security Database Service, Microsoft Azure Database Security, and Oracle Cloud Database Security are a few of the security technologies that have been implemented. These platforms offer a comprehensive suite of security features tailored to their respective ecosystems. Oracle Cloud Database Security, for instance, is specifically designed for Oracle users, offering advanced encryption and decryption processes that operate seamlessly within the Oracle Database environment. This not only ensures the protection of data but also facilitates a more efficient data management process. Additionally, Oracle enhances its security offering with data compression features, significantly reducing upload times and improving overall system performance. This is complemented by robust monitoring tools and protective measures against potential cyber-attacks and security breaches.

These technologies underscore the commitment of cloud service providers to maintaining the highest standards of data security. By continually innovating and adapting their security offerings, these companies not only safeguard their users' data but also foster a trust-based relationship with their clientele. The emphasis on security is a testament to the critical importance of protecting sensitive information in today's digital age, where cyber threats are

increasingly sophisticated and pervasive. As the cloud computing landscape evolves, the role of advanced security measures will only grow, ensuring that data stored in the cloud remains secure, accessible, and resilient against cyber threats.

Amazon Web Services (AWS) offers a comprehensive suite of features designed to enhance the security of relational databases through Amazon Relational Database Service (RDS). This platform facilitates the creation and management of databases with robust access control mechanisms, ensuring that only authorized instances can interact with the stored data. An essential component of Amazon RDS's security arsenal is Transparent Data Encryption (TDE), which plays a critical role in safeguarding data at rest by encrypting it to prevent unauthorized access.

Enhancing the security measures, AWS incorporates encryption services through Amazon CloudFront for sensitive data protection. CloudFront, AWS's content delivery network, ensures that data remains encrypted as it traverses the network. In scenarios where user data requiring encryption surpasses CloudFront's capabilities, AWS leverages the Lambda@Edge feature. This innovative solution extends the functionality of AWS Lambda, allowing for the execution of custom computing tasks closer to the user, thereby facilitating efficient data encryption at the network's edge.

CloudFront's encryption mechanism is underpinned by the RSA cryptographic system, renowned for its secure communication capabilities. This system enables the distribution of public keys across the CloudFront network's periphery, ensuring data encryption while maintaining the confidentiality of the corresponding private keys within the network's secure core. To bolster this

security framework, AWS has implemented Lambda@Edge functions that utilize asymmetric encryption with the RSA cryptosystem. These functions are adept at securing specific fields within HTTP(S) requests, further enhancing data security during transmission.

AWS's commitment to robust security measures extends to key management, utilizing the AWS Key Management Service (AWS KMS). This service offers centralized control over cryptographic keys, simplifying the process of key management while adhering to compliance and security policies. AWS KMS integrates seamlessly with other AWS services, including RDS and CloudFront, to provide a secure and compliant environment for managing sensitive data. Through these comprehensive security features, AWS ensures that data is not only securely stored but also protected during transmission, offering peace of mind to businesses and end-users alike.

Fig. 4 Field-level encryption process

Microsoft Azure offers confidentiality, integrity, availability of customer data, as well as transparent accountability. In addition, Microsoft Azure has also implemented a firewall system that is useful for limiting access to databases and other authentication procedures. Based on the IP address or origin of Virtual Azure network traffic, Microsoft Azure uses firewalls to deny network access to servers until access is specifically permitted. The originating IP address of each request determines whether IP firewall rules can provide access to the database. After that comes the authentication phase, which supports both Azure AD and SQL authentication on Azure SQL Database and SQL Managed Instances. For Azure AD principals, SQL Managed Instances additionally enable Windows Authentication.

Logging into an Azure SQL Database or Azure SQL Managed Instance involves a user authentication process known as SQL authentication, which relies on a traditional username and password combination. Alternatively, Azure Active Directory (Azure AD) authentication offers a more integrated method for connecting not only to Azure SQL Database and Azure SQL Managed Instance but also to Azure Synapse Analytics. This approach utilizes identities managed within Azure Active Directory, enabling a seamless authentication experience across various Azure services.

Azure AD authentication significantly streamlines the administration of database user identities and permissions. By centralizing the management within Azure Active Directory, administrators are afforded a unified platform for overseeing access controls and service interactions, enhancing security and operational efficiency. Furthermore, Azure SQL Managed Instances support Windows Authentication, employing Kerberos Authentication for Azure AD Principals. This capability extends the robustness of on-premises authentication methods to the cloud, allowing for secure and familiar login procedures for users.

The integration of Azure AD authentication across Azure's database services simplifies the security management landscape, providing administrators with powerful tools for securing data access. By leveraging Azure AD for authentication, organizations can ensure a consistent and secure user experience, while benefiting from the convenience of centralized identity management. This approach not only bolsters security but also facilitates a more streamlined administration of permissions and access within the Azure ecosystem.

Cyber attacks can be prevented before the violation occurs. To prevent data from cyber attacks, Almrif et al. (2019) stated three procedures: encryption, access control, and third-party audits. You can use the Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) and Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) for encryption. RSA is an asymmetric cryptographic algorithm that uses public and private keys, where the keys are linked systematically. AES is symmetric encryption for encrypting and decrypting messages. RSA will be used to exchange keys securely, and AES will encrypt and decrypt the actual message. Access Control is useful for granting limited access to users regarding network connections, data, and system files. So by using access control, we can set user control, whether the user can only view or make modifications. Third-party audits can use two methods: the Holomorphic linear authenticator (HLA) and Hash Message Authentication Code (HMAC). HLA is useful for keeping data stored in the cloud confidential during the audit process. HMAC is also useful for maintaining data privacy because by using HMAC, users must create a unique private key and use that key to access data. So, not just anyone can access the data.

Fig. 5 Procedures to maintain data security.

D. How can compromised databases be managed to restore the security of the data contained in the cloud database?

Security breaches that often occur are third parties breaking into the security system. Steps that can be taken as an end-user is to communicate with service providers. Think about service providers, are they involved in security breach leaks. The service provider takes the necessary steps to address it so that no additional security breaches occur. Service providers can work closely with our team of forensic experts to analyze security breaches that have occurred. Review logs to determine who had access to the data during the breach. Also, analyze who currently has access, determine if access is required, and limit access if not. Verify the type of information compromised and the number of people affected. When getting a forensic report, take the recommended corrective action as soon as possible.

Conclusion

Cloud is currently very successful and highly developed. The use of the cloud is certainly not free from various threats. One of the existing threats is privacy and security. Currently, there are still many issues regarding privacy and security, such as cases of data manipulation and hacking. To overcome this, there are two perspectives, namely from the side of the end user, as well as service providers. End users can report and communicate security breaches to service providers. Service providers have taken several steps to address privacy and data security issues. Amazon Web Services, provided by the Amazon company, uses a Relational Database Security (RDS) system that supports access control features. In addition, Amazon also provides a sensitive data encryption system using Amazon CloudFront. Microsoft Azure, provided by the Microsoft company, uses a firewall system to maintain privacy and security. This implemented firewall system will deny network access to servers until access is specifically permitted. The Oracle Cloud Database provided by Oracle uses a data encryption and decryption system that is directly handled by Oracle Database, Akinade et al, (2020).

Three procedures can be carried out to address privacy and security issues in cloud databases: encryption, access control, and third-party audits. The encryption algorithms that can be used are the Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) algorithm and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). Access Control is a procedure that needs to be done because access control is useful for giving limited access to users regarding network connections, data, and system files. Third-party audits can use two methods: the Holomorphic linear authenticator (HLA) and Hash Message Authentication Code (HMAC). Data privacy and security will be maintained by following these three procedures because not just anyone can access them. Future work could focus on refining

the scalability and elasticity of cloud-based databases. Research might delve into developing more intelligent and automated scaling mechanisms that dynamically adjust resources based on workload demands.

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